

Multi-objective evolutionary optimization for multi-period heat exchanger network retrofit

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ABSTRACT

Increase in energy efficiency and reduction in greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in industry are important steps towards a more sustainable economy. Due to the growing share of high value-added industries multi-period operation becomes more common in process industry. Therefore, retrofit of existing multi-period production plants is a key aspect towards more sustainable production processes. Hence, in this work, an existing two-level evolutionary algorithm using a genetic algorithm and a differential evolution for multi-period heat exchanger network retrofit is extended to consider GHG emissions as a second objective to the total annual cost (TAC). The multi-objective problem is addressed by incorporating a non-dominated sorting genetic algorithm (NSGA-II) and hypervolume indicators into the algorithm. By analyzing an industrial case study of a potato chips production, the results of the multi-objective optimization shows that GHG emissions can be reduced by 50%. However, compared to the single-objective optimization, TAC is increased by 27%. By selecting capital costs and operating costs as objectives instead, similar results to the single-objective optimization are achieved showing that the results are highly dependent on the selection of the objectives. Further, changes in utility costs and caused emissions have a high impact on the results.

1. Introduction

In view of the policy objective of net-zero carbon emissions, the deepest possible level of decarbonization must be achieved in all sectors. However, decarbonization of the industry sector is challenging due to the high complexity of the systems, heterogeneity, and high temperature levels. The systematic overall optimization of processes, in terms of their energy consumption, is referred to as Process Integration (PI) [1], with Heat Exchanger Networks (HEN) representing a key strategy [2]. Methods and tools are required for retrofitting pre-existing processes (brownfield), particularly multi-period processes, considering the overwhelming share of high value-added industries present in Switzerland (e.g., fine chemicals, pharma, food, beverages). Furthermore, in many Swiss companies, one single processing line is used to manufacture a portfolio of products, resulting in multi-period problems and representing additional challenges for PI. Methods are available for greenfield process design, e.g., Aguitoni et al. [3] used a bi-level optimization approach of Simulated Annealing and Differential Evolution (DE) to synthesize HEN. Pavão et al. [4] used metaheuristic

approach, based on Simulated Annealing and Rocket Fireworks Optimization, to synthesize and efficient multi-period HEN. The approach was coupled with post-optimization strategy to further improve the total annual cost. The challenges and research conducted to optimize multi-period processes have been reviewed by Stampfli et al. [5].

To reach higher levels of rigor, reproducibility, and comparability, HEN retrofit for multi-period processes based on mathematical optimization needs to be developed. Some research has already been conducted with mathematical-based optimization, which can be divided into stochastic and deterministic methods. Deterministic approaches are very challenging for HEN retrofit being a more complex sub-problem of HEN synthesis. The latter is already hard to solve without metaheuristic solvers due to the high complexity of mixed-integer non-linear characteristics of the problem. Considering, among other things, the increased availability of computational power, Toimil and Gómez [6] explained why there is a trend towards stochastic optimization methods, in particular towards metaheuristics. Metaheuristics combine simple local search methods (heuristics) with an algorithm to explore the search space to find an optimal or near-optimal solution.

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Nomenclature**Sets**

$C = \{0 \dots j \dots NC\}$	Set of cold streams
$E = \{0 \dots e \dots NE\}$	Set of heat exchangers
$H = \{0 \dots i \dots NH\}$	Set of hot streams
$K = \{0 \dots k \dots NK\}$	Set of enthalpy stages
$OP = \{0 \dots op \dots NOP\}$	Set of operating periods

Parameter

A	Heat exchanger area (m^2)
C	Cost factor (CHF)
c	Specific cost factor (e.g., CHF/ m^2)
CP	Heat capacity flow rate (kW/K)
f_d	Degression exponent (-)
h	Film heat transfer coefficient (W/(m^2 K))
i_r	Interest rate (-)
n	Depreciation period (y)
Q	Thermal energy (kWh)/ Quantity ([Q])
\dot{Q}	Heat flow (kW)
T	Temperatures ($^{\circ}C$)
w	Mass fraction (-)

Greek letters

ΔT	Temperature difference (K)
Δt	Time duration (h)
η	Efficiency coefficient (-)
ξ	Emission factor ($t_{CO_2/MWh}$)

Subscripts

a	Annualized
0	Base
cap	Capital
op	Operating
c	Cold side
h	Hot side
$init$	Initial
in	Inlet
out	Outlet
R	Removal
S	Supply
T	Target
U	Utility

Abbreviations

CAP	Annualized capital costs
COP	Operating costs/Coefficient of performance
CU	Cold utility
DE	Differential evolution
FOEN	Federal Office for the Environment
GA	Genetic algorithm
GHG	Greenhouse gas
HEN	Heat exchanger network
HEX	Heat exchanger
HU	Hot utility
MOO	Multi-objective optimization
NSGA-II	non-dominant sorting genetic algorithm

OF	Objective function
SOO	Single-objective optimization
SWS	Stage-wise superstructure
TAC	Total annual cost

A subgroup of metaheuristics is population-based algorithms such as Genetic Algorithms (GA) and DE. GA is a stochastic method based on the concept of survival of the fittest by comparing a population of solutions and selecting the best for further exploration. DE is similar to GA but designed to optimize continuous variables such as heat loads. Application of both GA/DE has been conducted by Stampfli et al. [7]. HEN problems can be divided into two classifications, single objective optimization (SOO), focusing on reducing total annual cost (TAC), and multi-objective optimization (MOO). MOO adds a layer of complexity to the optimization for the retrofit of existing HEN. Only limited research has been conducted on MOO of HEN retrofit, which is the focus of this paper. Sreepathi and Rangaiah [8] developed a MOO to retrofit HEN, where the objective functions are utility and investment costs. The authors used a program based on the non-dominated sorting genetic algorithm (NSGA-II), resulting in better MOO solutions. The authors then extended the work to retrofit HEN involving streams with variable heat capacity [9]. Their continuous approach to handling the variable heat capacity provided better and more practical solutions for the retrofit of HEN. Kang and Liu [10] developed a three-stage MOO procedure to retrofit multi-period HENs. The model has two objective functions, either total annual CO_2 emissions with capital costs for retrofit, number of substituted heat exchangers (HEXs), modification to the existing HEN structure, or additional heat transfer areas. With the current focus on reducing the GHG emissions of the industrial sector, this paper extends the work carried out by Stampfli et al. [5] to include GHG emissions in the MOO for multi-period HEN retrofit.

2. Problem statement

In previous work a two-stage genetic algorithm with differential evolution was developed to solve HEN retrofit for multi-period problems with minimal TAC [5]. A large focus of this work was on the practicality and implementation of the new designs. Therefore, additional practical constraints such as limiting the complexity by restricting stream splitting or considering additional costs for piping and control systems are considered in the optimization. As a result, the method aims to find practical implementable designs rather than global optimum designs.

An important factor for the environment in retrofit projects is the emitted GHG. The main cause of GHG emissions is the utility which is usually provided using natural gas boilers (Scope-2 emissions). Gray GHG emissions (Scope-3 emissions) are not considered as they usually account for a negligible share of the total emissions in HEN design [11]. Hence, this work extends the previous developed SOO to a MOO by considering GHG emissions as a second objective. By introducing a second objective, instead of having one single best solution, a Pareto front of non-dominated solutions will be generated. Therefore, the following research questions need to be addressed: (1) How can the existing evolutionary algorithm be extended to handle multi-objective problems and generate a Pareto front? and (2) What are the influences on the solution by considering GHG emissions as a second objective?

To address the research question (1), the algorithm will be extended by integrating an NSGA-II in the differential evolution to generate Pareto fronts of the heat load distributions for a given HEN topology. In the topology optimization, these fronts need to be compared with each other. Therefore, the concept of hypervolume indicators is used to create a fitness value for each Pareto front. To answer research question (2), the impact of the utility demand on the two objectives is to be analyzed as it is considered in both. Therefore, experiments are performed using different objectives (e.g. excluding operating costs (utility demand) in TAC).

Fig. 1. Overview of the two-stage evolutionary algorithm for multi-objective optimization.

3. Methods

For the MOO, the single-objective hybrid evolutionary algorithm for HEN retrofit for multi-period processes [7] was later extended to consider detailed mixer configurations [5]. In this work, it has been further developed to include GHG emissions as a second objective in the optimization. An overview of the algorithm is shown in Fig. 1 and summarized in Section 3.1. A detailed explanation of the algorithm, including its application, is provided by Stampfli et al. [5], and details on the implementation in Python 3.8.2 using the library DEAP - Distributed Evolutionary Algorithms in Python [12] is provided by Stampfli et al. [13].

The hybrid evolutionary algorithm has two stages whereby in the top-stage, the topology of the HEN (discrete variables) is optimized using a GA. For every feasible HEN design, the DE in the sub-stage optimizes for the best heat load distribution over the network (continuous variables). Thereby, a population of potential solutions is evaluated using a HEN model. To determine the fitness of the solutions, the TAC is used. Constraints are implemented as following: (1) often violated constraints such as energy balances are handled using penalizing strategies, and (2) constraints which would create impossible solutions such as maximal possible heat load of a HEX are handled with decoding strategies. In this work, GHG emissions are introduced as a second fitness function. The functions needed to extend the existing algorithm are provided in Section 3.2. For the selection of the multi-objective fitness in the DE, the NSGA-II is used to produce a Pareto front in which every solution has a fixed HEN topology but different heat loads. The concepts of the NSGA-II selection and the integration into the DE are explained in Section 3.3. In the GA, topologies are evaluated. Therefore, the hypervolume for every Pareto front is calculated and used as its fitness. The hypervolume calculation and its integration in the GA are

Fig. 2. Superstructure for the mixer configurations whereas $T_{i,k}^{op}$ and $T_{j,k}^{op}$ are the enthalpy stage temperatures, and $T_{e,h,in}^{op}$, $T_{e,c,in}^{op}$, $T_{e,h,out}^{op}$, and $T_{e,c,out}^{op}$ are the inlet and outlet temperatures of the HEX which are manipulated by the selected mixer configuration and determined using the Chen's explicit solution approach [5,14].

explained in Section 3.4. The SOO as well as the MOO version of the algorithm are available online and published under an open source licence [15,16].

3.1. Heat exchanger network model

The HEN model introduced by Stampfli et al. [5,13] is reused in this work and summarized in this section. Yee and Grossmann [17] stage-wise superstructure (SWS) is used as a base of the model. It is extended with (1) an additional dimension of operating periods (OPs), (2) utility heat exchanger within the enthalpy stages, and (3) selection and calculation of detailed mixer configuration (superstructure for the mixer configurations is shown in Fig. 2) using the explicit solution of the logarithmic mean [14]. Therefore, (3) uses the Lambert W-function [18] to ensure feasible heat transfer in every OP. (4) In industry, non-process streams such as exhaust gas are often so-called soft streams which can, but do not have to be cooled down. Thus, the SWS model is extended to handle such streams, which have no fixed target temperature and no need for utility. To ensure practical results, additional constraints are added to the SWS: (1) the number of splits per stream and enthalpy stage can be limited to prevent an unnecessary number of splits (Spaghetti design) [19], and (2) to set limits on extreme temperatures (e.g., phase change) for every stream which cannot be exceeded or fallen short of, respectively. This constraint ensures feasible temperatures in the mixer configurations. The fitness of the retrofitted network is determined using the TAC as the objective function (OF), which is composed of capital and operating costs. Thereby, capital costs for adding or removing area, new HEXs, and new mixer configurations are considered. Further, the capital costs include modification costs for re-piping and re-sequencing of HEXs and resulting piping costs (depending on the plant layout). Finally, the utility costs are considered as the operating costs.

3.2. Extension to multi-objective optimization

The model described in Section 3.1 is extended for MOO by adding GHG emissions as a second OF. GHG emissions are based on utility consumption and can be determined by

$$GHG = \sum_{\forall op} (\dot{Q}_{HU,op} \xi_{HU,op} + \dot{Q}_{CU,op} \xi_{CU,op}) \Delta t^{op} \quad (1)$$

Thereby, \dot{Q}_{HU}^{op} and \dot{Q}_{CU}^{op} describe the hot and cold utility (HU and CU) demands, respectively, in an operating period (OP). ξ_{HU}^{op} and ξ_{CU}^{op} are

Fig. 3. (a) Exemplary Pareto fronts created by the NSGA-II selection. Multiple ranks of non-dominated Pareto fronts are created by ignoring the higher ranked fronts before. The 1st Pareto front points are marked with an “x” and 2nd Pareto front points are marked with an “o”. (b) Exemplary hypervolume indicator for two different Pareto fronts is shown. In this case, the front, including points marked with an “x”, has a higher area, resulting in a higher hypervolume indicator and thus a higher fitness.

CO₂ emission factors and Δt^{op} is the duration of the associated OP. The objective for the SOO is the TAC determined by

$$TAC = C_{cap,a} + C_{op,a} = C_{cap,a} + \sum_{\forall op} (\dot{Q}_{HU,op} c_{HU,op} + \dot{Q}_{CU,op} c_{CU,op}) \Delta t^{op} \quad (2)$$

whereby $C_{cap,a}$ is the annualized capital costs. The operating costs $C_{op,a}$ depend on the utility demands \dot{Q}_{HU}^{op} and \dot{Q}_{CU}^{op} in the same way as the GHG but using specific cost factor c_{HU}^{op} and c_{CU}^{op} instead of specific emission factor ξ_{HU}^{op} and ξ_{CU}^{op} . This similarity of both functions creates a dependency between both objectives. Therefore, its effect on the results must be analyzed and compared to alternative objectives. To omit distorting of the solutions due to the different order of magnitudes in objectives, both are referenced to the initial HEN:

$$OF_{TAC} = \frac{TAC_{init}}{TAC} \quad (3)$$

$$OF_{GHG} = \frac{GHG_{init}}{GHG} \quad (4)$$

3.3. Differential evolution with NSGA-II selection for Pareto optimization

For the extension to a MOO, the selection in the DE needs to be adapted so that the algorithm can select solutions based on two instead of only one objective using NSGA-II [20]. For a given HEN topology, non-dominated solutions (there is no solution that is fitter in one objective without being less fit in another objective) with different heat load distributions are selected in a Pareto front (see points marked

with an “x” in Fig. 3(a)). The NSGA-II algorithm stores multiple fronts. By ignoring the non-dominated solutions stored in the 1st front, a 2nd front (see points marked with an “o” on the diagram in Fig. 3(a)) can be generated, which is only dominated by solutions in the 1st front. The solutions are sorted using the generalized reduced run-time complexity non-dominated sorting algorithm [21]. During the optimization of the heat loads in the DE, the whole list with all the Pareto fronts is considered, but only the non-dominated Pareto front is returned to the GA.

3.4. Genetic algorithm with hypervolume indicator for Pareto selection

The DE returns a Pareto front of non-dominated solutions for every HEN topology. To compare the Pareto fronts between different topologies, the fitness of each front is quantified using hypervolume indicators [22]. Thereby a reference point, p_{ref} , that is worse than every point in all the Pareto fronts is set. To avoid distorting the results, both TAC and GHG emissions are relativized with Eqs. (3) and (4). The area between the reference point and each Pareto front is the hypervolume and thus indicates the quality of the Pareto front (see Fig. 3(b)). These hypervolumes are used as the topologies’ fitness for the GA selection process (the larger the area, the higher the fitness).

4. Industrial case study: potato chips production

To illustrate the application of the algorithm, a potato chips production plant (fritter line 1) from the Zweifel Pomy-Chips AG is analyzed by Fotsch [23]. It produces two types of chips: regular chips ($w_{oil} =$

Fig. 4. Flow chart of the fritter-line 1 plant for chips production. Stream temperatures correspond to the two OPs: regular chips/Cractive chips [5].

Fig. 5. Retrofitted HEN optimized by the MOO_{TAC,GHG} algorithm configuration.

0.35) and Cractive chips ($w_{oil} = 0.25$). A flow chart of the process is shown in Fig. 4, the process requirements and the utility data are listed in Tables A.1 and A.2. The GHG emission factors in Table A.2 are determined using data published by the Federal Office for the Environment [24] for emissions caused by natural gas, and by Krebs and Frischknecht [25] for emissions caused by the consumer electricity mix. A natural gas boiler supplies hot utility with an efficiency of 90% ($0.22 \text{ t}_{\text{CO}_2\text{e}}/\text{MWh}$), and a refrigeration unit provides cold utility with a COP of 5.90 ($0.02 \text{ t}_{\text{CO}_2\text{e}}/\text{MWh}$). It is important to note, that the published data by Fotsch [23] uses pseudo-utilities which are not updated with realistic utilities in order to produce comparable results. Related investment costs and match costs for retrofit are listed in Tables A.3 and A.4. A 10 y depreciation period and 5% interest rate are given for the cost evaluation. For the optimization, the practical constraints are limited as follows: the minimum temperature difference is set to $\Delta T_{min} = 2 \text{ K}$, the minimal possible heat load to $\dot{Q}_{min} = 10 \text{ kW}$, the maximum number of possible HEX is limited to $NE = 7$, the number of enthalpy stages is set to $NK = 3$, and the number of possible HEX within one split is limited to $\#E_{max} = 2$. To ensure comparability with the published results [5], the algorithm parameters are chosen to be similar. Only populations sizes are increased since with the additional objective function, a larger solutions space is to be explored. For the GA, the population size is set to 150, for the tournament selection, the best of 5 solutions is selected, the Hall of Fame size is set to 100, the crossover probability is set to 90%, the mutation probability is set to 10%, and the number of generations is set to 75. For the DE, the population size is set to 200, the Pareto front size is set to 20, the crossover probability is set to 90%, the perturbation factor is set to 0.5,

the number of generations is set to 100, and the number of generations without improvement is set to 5. The optimization was performed on a Linux-based server with 256 GB RAM, using 50 of the 128 available threads distributed over 64 CPU cores for parallel computing of the DE algorithm.

5. Results

The results are split in three sections. First, in Section 5.1 the MOO solution is compared to the SOO solution published by Stampfli et al. [5], then in Section 5.2, the influences of the different objectives on the results is analyzed, and finally, in Section 5.3, the performance of the algorithm is analyzed and compared to the SOO algorithm configuration.

5.1. Comparison of the multi-objective to single-objective optimization

The resulting topology of the MOO, as shown in Fig. 5, is similar to the SOO result (shown in Fig. 6). It is important to notice that HEXs 3-7 are new, and therefore interchangeable without causing additional cost. For the MOO design, there is no process internal utility HEX. Although, the stream matches are identical, on process stream H₁, the order of the two last HEX (in declining temperature direction) is exchanged. In contrast to the SOO design, the MOO design re-uses HEX 2 from the initial design. Therefore, its HEX area needs to be increased by 8.6 m². Further, the placement of HEX 1 has changed and therefore, needs to be re-piped. In the SOO design, HEX 1 was not modified at all. In Table 1, the needed area to ensure feasible heat transfer in

Fig. 6. Retrofitted HEN optimized by the SOO_{TAC} algorithm configuration [5].

Table 1
Comparison of areas between the best found solution and the initial solution.

HEX	Initial design			SOO _{TAC}			MOO _{TAC,GHG}		
	$A_e^{op=1}$ m ²	$A_e^{op=2}$ m ²	$\Delta A_{e,not}$ (m ² h)/h	$A_e^{op=1}$ m ²	$A_e^{op=2}$ m ²	$\Delta A_{e,not}$ (m ² h)/h	$A_e^{op=1}$ m ²	$A_e^{op=2}$ m ²	$\Delta A_{e,not}$ (m ² h)/h
Process HEX									
1	14.0	16.0	1.26	13.8	15.2	0.88	16.0	15.1	0.33
2	2.4	2.5	0.06	–	–	–	0.0	11.1	6.97
3	–	–	–	0.0	8.4	5.28	13.9	15.5	1.01
4	–	–	–	15.0	15.0	0.00	13.8	5.0	3.27
5	–	–	–	0.0	0.2	0.13	–	–	–
6	–	–	–	0.0	19.1	12.00	–	–	–
7	–	–	–	13.0	4.3	3.23	0.0	16.2	10.18
Balance utility HEX^a									
CU ₁	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
CU ₂	5.6	3.9	0.63	1.4	0.4	0.37	1.2	0.4	0.30
HU ₁	–	–	–	0.1	0.1	0.00	0.0	0.1	0.06
HU ₂	–	–	–	0.1	0.1	0.00	0.0	0.1	0.06
HU ₃	0.8	0.4	0.15	0.2	0.1	0.04	0.2	0.1	0.04
HU ₄	0.0	4.8	3.02	0.0	0.1	0.06	0.0	0.0	0.00
HU ₅	0.0	0.5	0.31	0.0	0.1	0.06	0.0	0.1	0.06
$\sum_{\forall e} \Delta A_{e,not}$ ((m ² h)/h)			5.43			22.05			22.28
$\Delta A_{not,rel}$ ((m ² h)/(m ² h))			0.18			0.30			0.30

^aBalance utility HEX number is corresponding to the connected process stream (e.g., CU₁ at the end of H₁).

Table 2
Comparison of results for different objectives configurations (lowest TAC).

Configuration	TAC (CHF/y)	$C_{cap,a}$ (CHF/y)	$C_{op,a}$ (CHF/y)	GHG (tCO _{2e} /y)	Q_{HU} (MWh/y)	Q_{CU} (MWh/y)	OF _{TAC} (–)	OF _{cap,a} (–)	OF _{cop,a} (–)	OF _{GHG} (–)
Initial	141,080	0	141,080	331.68	1451	623	1.000	–	1.000	1.000
SOO _{TAC} ^a	48,198	35,419	12,780	30.14	132	55	2.927	3.983	11.039	11.004
MOO _{TAC,GHG}	61,341	54,453	6,888	15.04	62	48	2.300	2.591	20.482	22.053
MOO _{CAP,GHG}	67,726	28,737	38,989	81.09	330	314	2.083	4.909	3.618	4.090
MOO _{CAP,COP}	50,427	37,299	13,128	30.82	131	67	2.798	3.782	10.746	10.762
MOO _{CAP,COP} ^b	49,002	35,153	13,848	33.27	142	62	2.879	4.013	10.188	9.969

^aResults by Stampfli et al. [5].

^bManually inserted topology of SOO_{TAC}^a into the initial population.

every OP, are compared. The total area needed for the initial design is 30.2 m², for the SOO_{TAC} 72.9 m², and for the MOO_{TAC,GHG} 74.3 m². To determine how well the areas of the HEXs are utilized, the not-in-use area is weighted by its downtime

$$\Delta A_{e,not} = \sum_{\forall op} \left(\left(\max_{\forall op} (A_e^{op}) - A_e^{op} \right) \frac{\Delta t^{op}}{\sum_{\forall op} \Delta t^{op}} \right). \quad (5)$$

To compare the not-in-use area with other network configurations with different total areas, the not-in-use area is expressed as a ratio to the total area

$$\Delta A_{not,rel} = \frac{\sum_{\forall e} \Delta A_{e,not}}{\sum_{\forall e} \max_{\forall op} (A_e^{op})}. \quad (6)$$

By reducing the utility demand, the HEXs need to be more flexible to be able to compensate the different heat recovery in every OP. Therefore, it is expected that the higher the heat recovery and/or the number of HEX units in each OP is, the higher the difference in needed HEX areas between the OPs. This leads to a higher overall not-in-use areas. The results in Table 1 show the same conclusion, whereby the ratio of not-in-use area for the initial design of 0.18 is increased to 0.30 for the SOO_{TAC} and the MOO_{TAC,GHG} designs. Utility demands for the MOO_{TAC,GHG} is halved compared to the SOO_{TAC} solution (see Table 2, however by having one less HEX, the ratio of not-in-use area is insignificantly different.

5.2. Analysis of objectives

By including GHG emission as a second objective in the optimization, a linear dependency on utility demand between both objectives is introduced. This dependency is visible in the results by comparing

TAC and GHG emissions (see Fig. 7(a)). Rather than a Pareto front, a single best solution is found. By comparing the annualized capital costs and the GHG emissions in Fig. 7(b) the linear dependency is omitted, and a Pareto front can be identified (red curve). By comparing the SOO_{TAC} result from Stampfli et al. [5] to the MOO_{TAC,GHG} results shows that SOO_{TAC} is also a Pareto optimal solution for the MOO_{TAC,GHG} optimization (green dot). However, with the MOO_{TAC,GHG} no results in this region with similar TAC are found (see Fig. 7(b)). This can be explained by the fact that the MOO_{TAC,GHG} has a higher weight on the utility demand as they are represented in both objectives. Fig. 7(b), shows multiple sets of identifiable DE Pareto fronts. These fronts have all the same HEN topology but different heat load distributions. The range in annualized capital costs is relatively small compared to the range of GHG emissions. This indicates that changing the heat load distribution has a small effect on the HEX areas in contrast to the utility consumption. This concludes that GHG emissions can be reduced without extensive topology modification.

To analyze the influence of the weighting of the utility on the results, operating costs $C_{cap,a}$ are excluded from the TAC objective. The results are visualized in Fig. 8. Since utility demand has a lower weight on the results, operating costs are a higher portion of the TAC. Therefore, in Fig. 8(a), the linear dependency between TAC and GHG emissions is more evident. In Fig. 8(b), it can be seen that the Pareto front is shifted down from the blue dashed curve (MOO_{TAC,GHG}) to the red curve (MOO_{CAP,GHG}). Thereby, no results in the region of the SOO_{TAC} result (green point) are found. In contrast to the TAC and GHG emission optimization, the SOO_{TAC} result is not part of the Pareto front but dominates a large portion of the results. The results for MOO_{TAC,GHG} and MOO_{CAP,GHG} suggest that cost and emission factors strongly impact the weighting between costs and GHG emissions. By

Fig. 7. Optimization results using TAC and GHG emissions as objectives (MOO_{TAC,GHG}). The green point indicates the solution of the SOO_{TAC} from Stampfli et al. [5]. In (a), the linear dependency between TAC and GHG emissions is visible. In (b), the Pareto front (red curve) between annualized capital costs and GHG emissions can be identified.

analyzing the ratio of the impact of 1 MWh utility reduction on the TAC and GHG emissions, using the existing plant as a reference, it can be shown that utility has

$$\frac{GHG_{init}}{\xi_{HU} + \xi_{CU}} \frac{c_{HU} + c_{CU}}{TAC_{init}} = 1.176$$

more impact on the cost than on the GHG emissions. Thereby, the values for the initial TAC and GHG emissions (TAC_{init}, GHG_{init}) are listed in Table 2 and the values for the cost and emission factors (c_{HU}, c_{CU}, ξ_{HU}, ξ_{CU}) are listed in Table A.2.

To have the same impact of utility demand on the result, operating costs instead of GHG need to be considered (MOO_{CAP,COP}). The results are visualized in Fig. 9. It shows that the algorithm found a Pareto front close the SOO_{TAC} solution.

In Table 2, the results for the analyzed objective configurations are compared. Due to the higher weight on utility demand for the MOO_{TAC,GHG} optimization, the operating costs and GHG emissions are with 6,888 CHF/y and 15.04 t_{CO2e}/y, almost halved compared to the SOO_{TAC} with 12,780 CHF/y and 30.14 t_{CO2e}/y. As a result of the lower utility demand, the annualized capital costs for the MOO_{TAC,GHG} are with 54,453 CHF/y higher than the 35,419 CHF/y of the SOO_{TAC}, which results in 61,341 CHF/y TAC compared to 48,198 CHF/y. By excluding the operating costs in the objectives (MOO_{CAP,GHG}), the weight on the utility demand is lower than the SOO_{TAC}, leading with 38,989 CHF/y and 81.09 t_{CO2e}/y to the highest operating costs and GHG emissions.

However, with 28,737 CHF/y, the lowest annualized capital costs are found, resulting in TAC of 67,726 CHF/y. TAC and GHG emissions are both worse compared to the MOO_{TAC,GHG} solution and therefore this result is unlikely to be implemented.

By optimizing for annualized capital costs and operating costs (MOO_{CAP,COP}) the weighting is the same as for the SOO_{TAC}. The results of the optimization confirm this. The solution for MOO_{CAP,COP} has with 37,299 CHF/y slightly higher annualized capital costs than the SOO_{TAC} solution. Operating costs and GHG emissions are with 12,128 CHF/y and 30.82 t_{CO2e}/y the very similar to the SOO_{TAC} solution. This results in a slightly higher TAC of 50,427 CHF/y. To verify the MOO_{CAP,COP} solution, the best found topology of the SOO_{TAC} is manually inserted in the initial population resulting in similar costs and GHG emissions as for the MOO_{CAP,COP} and the SOO_{TAC} solutions.

In general, it cannot be said which objective configuration is best as it is another Pareto problem depending on which objective is more important. The differences in results based on the selection of the configuration of objectives also indicates that changes in cost and emission factors have a large impact on the solution.

5.3. Convergence analysis

In this section the convergence of the MOO algorithm is analyzed. To compare the results, with the SOO_{TAC} solution, the results

Fig. 8. The optimization results using annualized capital costs (C_{cap,a}) and GHG emissions as objectives (MOO_{CAP,GHG}). The green point indicates the solution of the SOO_{TAC} from Stampfli et al. [5]. In (b), the new Pareto front between annualized capital costs and GHG emissions (red curve) and the Pareto front from MOO_{TAC,GHG} (blue dashed curve), are visualized.

Fig. 9. The optimization results using annualized capital costs ($C_{cap,a}$) and operating costs ($C_{op,a}$) as objectives (MOO_{CAP,COP}). The green point indicates the solution of the SOO_{TAC} from Stampfli et al. [5]. In (b), the new Pareto front between annualized capital costs and GHG emissions (red curve) is drawn.

of MOO_{CAP,COP} is selected in order to guarantee the same weighting leading to similar results. Fig. 10 shows the convergence over the number of generations for TAC and GHG. In Fig. 10(a), TAC of the MOO_{CAP,COP} as well as SOO_{TAC} improve rapidly and stagnate over time. In contrast to the SOO_{TAC} which is constantly improving and reaching its best found solution after around 50 generations, MOO_{CAP,COP} stagnates after around 8 generations and reaches its best found solution at around 60 generations. This stagnation can be explained by analyzing Fig. 10(b). It can be seen that the GHG emissions have a very sharp convergence reaching its almost best found solutions already at around 8 generations. This means that after 8 generations the utility consumption and thus also operating costs are only improving slightly. Hence, improvement of TAC after generation 8 are mostly due to improvement of capital costs by changes in topology, HEX areas, and mixer configurations.

6. Conclusions

The hybrid two-level evolutionary-based algorithm for heat exchanger network (HEN) retrofit for multi-period processes using genetic algorithm (GA) for topology optimization and differential evolution (DE) for heat load optimization has been extended from single-objective optimization (SOO) to multi-objective optimization (MOO) by introducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions as a second objective. Therefore,

the algorithm is extended using a non-dominated sorting genetic algorithm (NSGA-II) and hypervolume indicators to implement a Pareto optimization.

With the introduction of the second objective, the weight on the utility demand is increased because the utility consumption causes operating costs as well as GHG emissions. Hence, the MOO result has 27% higher TAC but 50% lower GHG emissions compared to the SOO result. By excluding the operating costs from the TAC, the weight on utility demand is decreased resulting in 169% higher GHG emissions and 41% higher TAC compared to the SOO result. This can be explained by the fact that with the cost and emission factors of the analyzed case study, the reduction of utility demand has a 18% higher impact on operating costs than GHG emissions. To achieve comparable results to the SOO capital costs and operating costs need to be selected as an important decision factor alongside costs and energy consumption. The application to the industrial case study has shown that developed algorithm is useful tool providing the industry with the needed information for the decision-making process during the conceptual phase of a retrofit project.

In conclusion, the selection of the objectives is a Pareto problem. It depends on the project goals if GHG emissions or TAC are more critical and should be prioritized. It is important to highlight the influence of the weighting on the results. This influence also shows that a change in cost or emission factors has a large impact on the solution. Energy

Fig. 10. Convergence of the MOO_{CAP,COP} optimization over the number of topology generations. Whereby, (a) shows the convergence of the TAC in comparison with the SOO_{TAC} algorithm (dashed curve) and (b) shows the convergence of the GHG emissions.

prices might vary between different sites due to other energy provider and GHG emission depend on the technologies used to provide the utilities. Hence, a change in energy prices or the use of different utility systems, have a significant influence on the final design of the HEN.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jan A. Stampfli: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Visualization. **Benjamin H.Y. Ong:** Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Donald G. Olsen:** Data curation, Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Beat Wellig:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **René Hofmann:** Resources, Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The algorithm is available online [15,16] and the case study data provided in the Appendix.

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Appendix. Process requirements and cost data for the potato chips production case study

Table A.1

Process requirements of the fritter line 1 for the regular chips and the cractive chips OP [5].

Stream	#	T_S °C	T_T °C	$T_{extr.}$ °C	CP kW/K	h W/(m ² K)
Regular chips OP (4,410 h/y)						
Vapor heating	C ₁	136	229	500	2.51	400
Boiler air pre-heating	C ₂	10	40	300	1.52	100
Make-up oil pre-heating	C ₃	24	176	210	0.37	400
Degreaser air heating	C ₄	–	–	–	–	–
Degreaser direct steam evaporation	C ₅	–	–	–	–	–
Waste gas cooling ^a	H ₁	280	30	30	14.81	400
Chips cooling	H ₂	151	24	24	0.79	300
Cractive chips OP (2,610 h/y)						
Vapor heating	C ₁	125.9	226.1	500	2.45	400
Boiler air pre-heating	C ₂	10	40	300	1.48	100
Make-up oil pre-heating	C ₃	24	166	210	0.18	400
Degreaser air heating	C ₄	163.4	174	500	23.31	100
Degreaser direct steam evaporation	C ₅	144.9	145.1	145.1	940.00	5000
Waste gas cooling ^a	H ₁	270.1	30	30	14.3	400
Chips cooling	H ₂	150	24	24	0.55	300

^aSoft streams.

Table A.2

Utility data (pseudo-utilities) [5].

Utility	T_S °C	T_T °C	h W/(m ² K)	c_U CHF/MWh	ξ_U t_{CO_2eq}/MWh
Heating steam (HU)	300	299	5,000	80	0.22 ^a
Cooling water (CU)	0	1	2,000	40	0.02 ^b

^aNatural gas boiler ($\eta = 0.9$).

^bRefrigeration unit (COP = 5.9).

Table A.3

Modification cost factors (including Lang factors [26]: 3 for adding equipment (c_A); 1.1 for removing equipment (c_R)). Only cost for the removal of an equipment is listed, if it is existing (HEX, and admixer) [5].

Equipment	C_0 CHF	Q [Q]	c_A CHF/Q	c_R CHF/Q	d_f –
HEX	0	A (m ²)	1,731	635	0.61
Split	0	–	40,000	–	1.00
Bypass	0	–	40,000	–	1.00
Admixer	0	–	40,000	14,666	1.00
Re-pipe	0	–	68,000	–	1.00
Re-sequence	0	–	68,000	–	1.00

Depreciation period $n = 10$ y; interest rate $i_r = 5\%$.

Table A.4

Match cost matrix (including utility streams) in CHF [5].

H \ C	C ₁	C ₂	C ₃	C ₄	C ₅	CU
H ₁	0	1,500	2,100	2,100	2,100	0
H ₂	900	3,000	600	300	300	0
HU	0	0	0	0	0	0

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